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Ghost Futures

by [Enrike Hurtado](#)

Digital Album

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- ▶ 1. [The Slow Cancellation of the Future \(New Cross\)](#) 11:39
- ▶ 2. [A Million Membranes to Break Through \(Lewisham\)](#) 05:18
- ▶ 3. [Everything Totally Taken Out It \(Depford\)](#) 13:03
- ▶ 4. [Coda: Inscapable](#) 05:50

SOLD OUT

Ghost Futures _ Música por Enrike Hurtado _ Diseño por Iñaki Garmendia _ Masterizado por Juan Carlos Blancas _ Grabado por Crystal Mine _ Burgos - Bilbao, 2023. Puedes comprarlo aquí: crystalmine@disroot.org . C40 #anticopyright

Ghost Futures parte de una serie de collages y fotografías realizadas por Enrike Hurtado en torno a 1997-98 cuando vivía en el sudeste de Londres. En 2022 Enrike plantea una serie de piezas que ensamblan entrevistas de programas televisivos y conferencias sobre música popular (y otras artes) junto con texturas y ruidos generadas a partir de música de finales de los 90. Revolución, futuro, libertad... ¿Cómo evitar que nuestra imaginación acabe alimentando al sistema?

Ghost Futures is based on a series of collages and photographs taken by Enrike Hurtado around 1997-98 when he was living in South East London. In 2022 he prepares a series of pieces that assemble interviews from television programmes and conferences on popular music (and other arts) together with textures and noises generated from music from the late 1990s. Revolution, future... [more](#)

released May 4, 2023

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Tags

[experimental](#) [anticopyright](#) [Burgos](#)

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Crystal Mine
Burgos, Spain

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by Nick Schofield

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(Original Motion Picture Soundtrack)
by Duval Timothy & CJ Mirra

Divided by Dusk
by Magda Drozd

Weimar
by Mary Ocher

Muslimgauze-Muslimlahore
by Muslimgauze

Meditations
by David Shea

Yeah, mostly
by Will Epstein

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